

Conductometric Studies on the Dissociation Constants of Salicylic and Substituted Salicylic Acids in Methanol-Water Mixtures

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The pK_a values of salicylic acid and 5-chloro- and 5-bromo-salicylic acids in methanol+water mixtures (8–87.9 wt % of methanol) were determined using conductometric method suggested by Gelb with slight modification. The results have been further verified by Fuoss-Kraus method. The limitations of the present state of knowledge of solution chemistry in accounting the variations of the dissociation constants with solvent composition have been stressed.

THE role of solvents on the ionization constants of weak acids is not well understood. The changes in pK -values with solvent composition cannot be explained in terms of Born equation¹ or modified equations^{2–5}. It has been well emphasized that the changes in ΔpK values can only be accounted for in terms of 'electrostatic' and 'non-electrostatic' parts^{6,7}. But in view of the limited accuracy of the equations and in absence of accurate values of radii of ions particularly for the unsymmetrical ones, it is very difficult to realize the full significance of 'non-electrostatic' parts or medium effects, of the solvents.

These imply the usefulness of determining the dissociation constants of more acids and bases in mixed solvents for a proper knowledge of 'electrostatic' and 'non-electrostatic' parts and to have a proper correlation of the results.

We have emphasized previously^{8,9} the limitations of determining the dissociation constants in mixed solvent using H electrode or glass electrodes. These are :

a) The e.m.f. of hydrogen electrode is taken to be zero in all the solvent systems. This generates quite a large number of unrelated pH or e.m.f. scales¹⁰. The values of dissociation constants are obviously difficult to correlate.

b) Liquid junction potentials, asymmetry potentials and responses of the glass electrodes do not change with solvent composition.

Furthermore, the reliability of the results should be checked by different methods. The search for a suitable alternative showed that the method suggested by Gelb¹¹ could be utilised with success in mixed solvents with slight modification.

We report in this communication, the dissociation constants of salicylic acid, 5-chloro- and 5-bromo-salicylic acids in methanol+water mixtures (0–87% by wt of methanol) by Gelb's method. The results have been further verified by Fuoss and Kraus^{12,13} method involving no assumptions.

Experimental

Methanol (G.R., E. Merck) was purified and the weight percentages of methanol in the solvent mixtures were determined in the same way described before. Conductivity water was prepared in the way given before^{14,15}. Precautions were taken to prevent the solvents from contamination with CO_2 . Salicylic acid (G.R., E. Merck), 5-chlorosalicylic acid (BDH) and 5-bromo salicylic acid (BDH) were purified from alcohol. The purity of the acids was tested by melting point determination. The acids and $HClO_4$ (G.R., E. Merck) were estimated volumetrically using NaOH (G.R., E. Merck) standardized with succinic acid (G.R., E. Merck) and Potassium hydrogen phthalate in the usual way.

The experimental details are the same as described before^{8,9}.

Conductance measurements were made with the aid of a Leeds-Northrup model 4959 conductance bridge with a sensitivity of $\pm 0.1\%$. A 50–60 cycle signal was employed. A dip-type Philips conductance cell with cell constant ($\theta = 0.85 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) was utilized. The measurements were done at $25 \pm 0.02^\circ$.

Results

The dissociation constant of a weak acid HA

in presence of completely dissociated HClO_4 can be written as

$$H = \frac{\alpha(C_{\text{HA}} + C_{\text{HClO}_4}) \times f_{\pm}^2}{(1 - \alpha)} \quad (2)$$

The terms have their usual significance. However, when the conductances $1/R$ (of the mixture containing HClO_4 and HA) and $1/R^*$ (blank solutions containing HClO_4 only) are equal, we have,

$$C_{\text{HClO}_4} \cdot \Lambda'_{\text{HClO}_4} + \alpha C_{\text{HA}} \Lambda'_{\text{HA}} = C^*_{\text{HClO}_4} \cdot \Lambda'^*_{\text{HClO}_4} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{and } C_{\text{HClO}_4} + \alpha C_{\text{HA}} = C^*_{\text{HClO}_4} \quad (4)$$

assuming

$$\Lambda'_{\text{HClO}_4} = \Lambda'^*_{\text{HClO}_4} \text{ and } \Lambda'_{\text{HClO}_4} = \Lambda'_{\text{HA}}$$

in aqueous and mixed solvents from which α can be calculated.

Λ' = Equivalent conductance of the completely dissociated electrolyte at any ionic strength.

Λ = equivalent conductance of the electrolyte at that ionic strength i.e., $\Lambda = \alpha \Lambda'$

($\alpha = 1$, in case of HClO_4 and * indicates the quantities in blank solutions).

Further improvement of K values is possible taking

$$\alpha = (C^*_{\text{HClO}_4} - C_{\text{HClO}_4}) / \beta C_{\text{HA}} \quad (5)$$

Where $\beta = \Lambda'_{\text{HA}} / \Lambda'_{\text{HClO}_4}$

β can be approximated to $\Lambda^{\circ}_{\text{HA}} / \Lambda^{\circ}_{\text{HClO}_4}$

at low concentrations of the acid and at low ionic strengths.

$\Lambda^{\circ}_{\text{HClO}_4}$ values have been taken from our previous experiment.

The initial values of $\Lambda^{\circ}_{\text{HA}}$ and K of weak acids in mixed solvents were determined from the plot of ΛC against $1/\Lambda$ in the usual way. The improvement of $\Lambda^{\circ}_{\text{HA}}$ and K values were made using the method of Fuoss and Kraus^{1,2,3} utilizing the relationship

$$F(Z)/\Lambda = \frac{1}{K \Lambda^{\circ 2}} \cdot \frac{\Lambda c f_{\pm}^2}{F(Z)} + \frac{1}{\Lambda^{\circ}} \quad (6)$$

as described before^{6,9,10}.

The $\log f_{\pm}$ values were calculated from the equation

$$-\log f_{\pm} = A \sqrt{\alpha C} \quad (7)$$

using the appropriate values of A .

Discussions

The average values of Λ° and pK of salicylic acids in methanol + water mixtures are given in table 1. Considering the limitations, the results obtained from titration method and Fuoss-Kraus^{1,2,3} method agree fairly well. In spite of the limited accuracy of extrapolated Λ° values, the results seem to be quite in order. Λ° values decrease as the percentage of organic solvent increases as noted by Shedlovsky et al¹⁷. Λ° values have been found to be higher in methanol + water compared to those in ethanol + water mixtures as expected.

The pK -values of salicylic acid and substituted salicylic acids have been found to be higher in methanol + water mixtures than in the corresponding ethanol + water mixtures¹⁸ at low percentages (upto about 60 wt %). This is anomalous in view of lower dielectric constants of ethanol + water mixtures compared to methanol + water mixtures and generally the pK -values increase with decrease in dielectric constant. However, the reverse trend is observed at higher percentages as expected. The expected trend is also observed in case of benzoic acids.

Though most of the results (the pK -values in ethanol + water mixtures and the corresponding pK -values in methanol + water mixtures) are within the limits of our experimental accuracy, but the anomalous results may be due to the change in the nature of hydrogen-bonding.

It is well-known that the dielectric constant alone is incapable of accounting for the change in pK -values and the main factor being solute-solvent interactions of which the hydrogen-bonding will be of special importance in the present case. It may be that the internal hydrogen-bond formation in stabilizing the anion is more pronounced in ethanol + water mixtures than in methanol + water mixtures.

A linear relationship is observed when pK s are plotted against mole-fraction of organic solvent or $1/\epsilon$ upto about 65 wt % of organic solvents. Deviations are observed at high percentages. Slight improvement occurs when the activities of water are taken into consideration as suggested by Yasuda¹⁹.

The approximate difference of pK values in mixed solvents can be had from Born¹ equation

$$\Delta pK = pK(S) - pK(W) = 121.6 (1/\epsilon - 0.0128) (1/r_A + 1/r_B) \quad (8)$$

TABLE 1

Wt. % of MeOH	Mole fraction of MeOH	1/ε × 100	Temp. 25°C Λ° in mhos cm ² /equiv.				Av. pKa of Salicylic			Av. pKa of C.S.A.			Av. pKa of B.S.A.		
			HClO ₄	Salicylic	C.S.A.	B.S.A.	(a)	(a*)	(b)	(a)	(a*)	(b)	(a)	(a*)	(b)
0.0	0.0000	1.27	415.0	400.0	395.0	394.1	3.04	3.05	3.04	2.65	2.66	2.66	2.61	2.62	2.66
8.0	0.0466	1.33	381.0	362.4	361.0	364.0	3.12	3.16	3.16	2.76	2.78	2.77	2.75	2.78	2.79
16.0	0.0968	1.40	331.3	309.0	305.2	209.0	3.24	3.37	3.37	2.80	2.87	2.90	2.86	2.92	2.95
25.2	0.1593	1.48	280.5	269.0	26.82	264.0	3.45	3.56	3.58	3.04	3.10	3.12	3.06	3.13	3.16
34.4	0.2279	1.57	228.0	219.0	220.0	219.5	3.54	3.64	3.69	3.17	3.27	3.28	3.19	3.28	3.32
44.7	0.3126	1.69	195.1	186.0	184.6	184.0	3.74	3.85	3.87	3.43	3.42	3.44	3.32	3.45	3.48
54.2	0.3997	1.84	171.7	155.8	156.0	158.0	3.92	4.00	4.05	3.53	3.59	3.60	3.52	3.59	3.62
64.1	0.5000	2.01	151.5	137.0	134.0	135.2	4.18	4.30	4.30	3.70	3.75	3.78	3.63	3.73	3.74
75.9	0.6392	2.25	131.0	114.4	113.5	116.0	4.48	4.50	4.56	3.92	3.95	4.02	3.95	4.00	4.03
87.9	0.8034	2.57	117.5	96.2	93.5	93.0	4.73	4.79	4.82	4.15	4.20	4.23	4.17	4.22	4.28

C.S.A. = 5-chlorosalicylic acid, B.S.A. = 5-bromosalicylic acid.
 a) pKa from the plot of ΛC vs 1/Λ, a*) pKa from Fouss-Kraus method.
 b) pKa from titration method.

where r_A & r_H represent the radii of acid anion & proton respectively. However, pK values calculated with $r_H = 0.86 \text{ \AA}^2$ and $r_A = 2.0 \text{ \AA}^{1.0}$ do not agree with the experimental values. The reasons are—(i) uncertain values of radii of ions, (ii) approximate nature of the Born equation, (iii) solute-solvent interactions and solvent basicity of uncertain magnitude affecting the results. The improvement is only marginal even if the local variations in dielectric constant within the solvation shells have been taken into consideration²⁻⁵. Even the theory of Hiromi²⁰ which takes into account the particular geometry and charge distribution within organic ion is inadequate as it predicts the variation of pK against $1/\epsilon$.

The difference between $[pK(S) - pK(W)]_R$ and $[pK(S) - pK(W)]_O$ [Where R = Substituted acid and O = unsubstituted acid] should be linearly related to $1/\epsilon$ as expected from the equation but actually not observed in practice.

$$[pK(S) - pK(W)]_R - [pK(S) - pK(W)]_O = 121.6 (1/\epsilon - 0.0128) (1/r_{AR} - 1/r_{AO}) \quad (9)$$

The equation cancels the term due to free-energy of transfer of H^+ ions and therefore, is likely to be obeyed

as the observed deviations have generally been assumed to be due to the free-energy of transfer of proton from water to different alcohol mixtures which is not a linear function of $1/\epsilon^{21}$.

Ohtaki²² has shown that a good account of the variation of pK for charged acids in alcohol-water mixtures can be obtained by combining the Born equation with terms which depend upon a knowledge of hydronium-alkoxonium ion equilibria in the solvent mixtures. The treatment reduces to equation (9) for the comparison of medium effects for two charged acids. However, the relationship fails and the treatment does not help much for the comparison of the relative behaviour of pair of acids as observed by Rochester²¹.

The failure of the equation is also apparent as the value of the dielectric constant is known to be a function of radii of ions^{2-5, 23}.

The results indicate that the proper knowledge of the 'non-electrostatic' contributions resulting from ion-solvent interactions, solvent-basicity, hydrogen-bonding etc. are necessary to explain the variations of pK with solvents,

The ΔpK_a ($=pK_s - pK_a$) values or "medium effects of all these acids are the same within the limits of experimental accuracy as expected in the ionizing group, charge and sizes are almost the same in all the cases. A slight variation in ΔpK values may result from the change in the ratios of water in the solvation shells of anions having polar substituents compared to uncharged acids leading to a favourable free energy change. The structural modification of solvation shells due to ionic solvation will have profound effect.

But from the results we are yet unable to throw more light on the role of solvents on the dissociation constants of acids and bases. We also emphasize the need of determining dissociation constants of weak acids by conductometric methods with more accurate bridges and better facilities. These possibly may evolve a suitable and unambiguous method of determining the dissociation constants in aqueous and mixed solvents free from assumptions.

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